

Modular programme for Education and Training

YOUTH SPORT COACH

*M#1 Daily Physical Activity and Sport
& Motor Skills Assessment*

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TECHNICAL SHEET

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Six Core Modules of EduPASS Modular Programme for Education and Training for Youth Sport Coach

The following are the proposed six core modules for Youth Sport Coaches education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Youth Sport Coaches should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for YSC education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Coaching Children Curriculum \(ECCC\)](#). The ECCC, in turn, is built around the Primary Functions of the Coach as described in the European Sport Coaching Framework (2017) ([CoachLearn | European Sport Coaching Framework](#)) and the [International Sport Coaching Framework \(2013\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing a Youth Sport Coach education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS YSC education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment	<p>Daily physical activity, Movement, Play, and Sports (PAMPS) has many benefits for children – physically, psychologically, emotionally and cognitively. In this context, the development of physical literacy of each child is essential.</p> <p>Awareness of trends in children’s participation levels, physical activity guidelines, the needs and wants of children and how to engage with children in age-appropriate ways, will assist the coach.</p> <p>Knowledge on the growth and development of children in all aspects (socially, physically, emotionally and cognitively) is essential.</p> <p>This should be underpinned by the coach’s personal values and beliefs about the role of PAMPS for children and young people and about what constitutes ‘good practice’ (their coaching philosophy).</p> <p>To support individual children and to develop programmes based on their needs, the ability to assess motor skills will guide this work.</p>

<p>2</p>	<p>Principles of Coaching Children</p>	<p>The principles of good coaching practice with children should be used by the Youth Sport Coach (YSC). These form the basis for the 10 principles of the ICOACHKIDS Pledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principle 1 — Be child-centred • Principle 2 — Be holistic • Principle 3 — Be inclusive • Principle 4 — Make it fun and safe • Principle 5 — Prioritise the love for sport over learning sport • Principle 6 — Focus on foundational skills • Principle 7 — Engage parents positively • Principle 8 — Plan progressive programmes • Principle 9 — Use difference methods to enhance learning • Principle 10 — Use competition in a developmental way <p>The YSC develops a programme based on their needs and the stage of development of children, based on the principles of coaching children.</p> <p>The YSC seeks to optimise the environment in which the programme occurs. The ability to navigate this can be guided by the Youth Sport Compass. The compass has 4 pillars – Developmental, Motivational, Caring and Social Safety – which can guide the YSC.</p> <p>The organisational and social context of the programme, including the participants (children/parents/club) should be taken into account.</p>
<p>3</p>	<p>Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding</p>	<p>The Youth Sport Coach builds positive and effective relationships and works with a group of participants (children, club, school, parents, federation and other levels) and takes responsibility for the realisation of the common and individual objectives, and to achieve the programme and club goals. Hearing ‘the Voice’ of each child is an important component of this.</p> <p>Safeguarding and child protection must underpin the establishment of a safe environment for children in sport.</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>Fundamental Movement Skills and Play</p>	<p>Children should develop foundational motor skills to underpin their love of being active and to have the competence to engage in a range of activities. The development of fundamental movement (balance, agility, coordination, speed) and motor skills (run, move, jump, land, throw, catch, kick, etc) is essential, and is supported by contexts that engage children in fundamental play activities.</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Hands-on Coaching</p>	<p>The Youth Sport Coach needs to develop their personal coaching skills and coaching tools. These include - introducing activities, demonstration, set-up and stand back, questioning and listening, feedback and reflection.</p> <p>Based on the principles of coaching children, inclusive coaching, and development of fundamental motor skills, the YSC needs to plan and organise suitable and challenging practices and attendance at events, using effective pedagogy and methodology, to promote the learning and improvement of children.</p>

		<p>The development of personal coaching skills and the planning of practices/events need to be practiced both with peers and in experiential learning situations with children. Thus, the aim of this module is to help craft safe learning experiences where “coaches learn how to coach by coaching”. Those hands-on coaching experiences enable coach learners to prepare coaching, engage in, and have an opportunity to receive feedback and engage in self-reflection about their coaching practice.</p>
<p>6</p>	<p>Plan, Reflect and Learn</p>	<p>The environment, which Youth Sport Coaches contribute to, can be welcoming and inclusive to all children. Individual coaches can provide this in their personal coaching and can also contribute to a club / school having child-centred values and policies. The Youth Sport Coach will examine their personal coaching philosophy and a means to support a club / school to adopt child-centred values and policies.</p> <p>Reflection on practice has been identified as a key means of learning and ongoing development for coaches. This can be supported by engaging with others and to a club / school being a learning environment for coaches (as well as children). Reflection is a learned skill and the Youth Sport Coach will reflect on their practice individually, with co-coaches and with a mentor.</p>

Youth Sport Coach – Programme Outcomes

The action-oriented outcomes and results for coaches for the complete module programme for Education and Training are presented below. The outcomes have been adapted from the [European Sport Coaching Framework](#) (Human Kinetics, 2017).

	The Youth Sport Coach in training will have taken the first steps towards being able to:
Coaching Vision and Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a suitable vision for the programme relevant to the participants (and in line with institutional priorities) • Make effective and informed decisions relating to the planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of mid- to long-term programmes (of practice and competition) based on (institutional and) participant needs • Encourage adopting sustainable, life-long engagement in PAMPS / Daily PA
Shape the Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to identify, reflect on and challenge prevailing beliefs, values and assumptions within the coaching environment to establish a suitable culture for PAMPS • Know how to create an environment where all children feel safe and included • Know about and be able to identify potential dangers for children in sport • Contribute to crafting and upholding a coaching environment / club / school that has child-centred values and policies • Build a community of practice and contribute to the on-going learning of other coaches and that where they coach is a learning environment for coaches.
Building Positive Relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to establish and maintain an ethical, effective, inclusive and empathetic relationship with children and other stakeholders (e.g., parents) • Understand how to appreciate physical, mental and cultural diversity in children and adapt PAMPS practice accordingly
Coaching Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct (comprehensive) needs analyses (assessments) for individual children (and/or teams) in order to design and deliver tailored coaching programmes, taking into account children needs and capabilities (in the context of wider programmes, curricula, policies and targets) • Understand how to select, design and justify appropriate pedagogy, practice and communication methods to facilitate the short, medium and long-term learning needs of children • Understand the core elements of multi skills or of their chosen sport(s) at the key stages of child development • Know how to deliver a series of coaching sessions in the context of medium term and long term planned programmes of practice and competition using a

	wide range of appropriate learning modes for children and coaching behaviours
Decision Making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand how to conduct an informed analysis of own performance and of the performance of children towards ensuring continuous progress and improvement • Understand how to make good in-action and post-action decisions to increase the chances of reaching short-, mid- and long-term objectives • Apply knowledge of fundamentals of movement, fundamental movement skills and fundamental game skills to create practices that lead to short-term and long-term learning, including play • Apply knowledge of motor skill development for children and youth, including the stages/phases of skill development and the impact of growth and maturation
Coaching Review and Reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct an insightful analysis of coaching practice to make informed judgements relating to the efficacy of the learning environment established • Reflect on their personal coaching knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and practice, with the aim of continuously improving • Continuously build and engage with a network of coaches / coach developers to keep reviewing and building personal best-practices in coaching children, seeking supervised hands-on coaching contexts

Module Structure

Core Module	Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment
Module Number	1
Core Module Aim	The aim of the core module is to pass knowledge and attitudes about the benefits of daily physical activity; to learn skills about monitoring and assessing the current status of individual motor and sport skills development of children and adolescents; to know about young people’s physical development at risk; to value daily physical activities for health, well-being and holistic development of their personality.
Module Description	The module is structured into 3 courses, Course No.1 is a theoretical course to gain knowledge; course No.2 is a practical course to learn and experience skills; course No. 3 is a mix of theoretical and practical course content to apply knowledge and skills to given practical examples. As a part of this course attitudes should be shaped to help and to assist young people to get regular physical active each day for at least 60 min.
Module Duration	30 hours (including 14 hours of Self-Directed Learning)
Facilities and Equipment	Seminar room and gym
Methodology	Class based and gym based presentations, during which coach learners will be involved in learning and experiencing coaching skills (plan, organize, observe, demonstrate, analyze, provide feedback, evaluate), in a preliminary way, so as to contribute to the sporting process as an junior coach.
Coaching Materials	Textbook, toolkits, test manuals, logbook / reflection book
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gallahue, D., & Ozmun, J. (2006). <i>Understanding Motor Development: Infants, Children, Adolescents, Adults</i> (6th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill. • Haywood, K.M.; Getchell, N. (2020). <i>Life Span Motor Development</i>, 7th ed.; Human Kinetics: Champaign, IL, USA, 2020 • Malina, R., Bouchard, C. & Bar – Or, O. (2004). <i>Growth, Maturation and Physical Activity</i> (Second Edition). Champaign: Human Kinetic, Illinois • Santrock, J. (2008). <i>Life–Span Development</i> (Eleventh edition) New York: McGraw – Hill Book Company • Steene-Johanessen, Hansen, Dalene, et al. (2020). Variations in accelerometry measured physical activity and sedentary time across Europe - harmonized analyses of 47,497 children and adolescents. <i>Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act</i>, 17(1):38. doi: 10.1186/s12966-020-00930-x. • World Health Organization. (2019). <i>Guidelines on Physical activity, sedentary behavior, and sleep for children under the age of 5</i> https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/325147/WHO-NMH-PND-2019.4-eng.pdf • World Health Organization (2018). Physical Activity: http://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/physical-activity; 2018 • International Physical Performance Test Profile webpages: (KIT - Startseite)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MOBAK website: MOBAK • Physical Literacy (isca.org) • Physical-Literacy-Tools-for-Assessment-in-Canada.pdf (physicalliteracy.ca) 					
Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Youth Sport Coach Programmes					
Module structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 1.1: Needs & benefits of daily physical activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Seminar ○ 6 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 1.2: Monitoring and assessment of fundamental movement skills and sport skills <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Seminar ○ 4 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 1.3: Applying toolkits and test items for measurement and assessment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 6 h Workshop/Practical Experience ○ 4 h Self-Directed Working hours 					
Learning outcomes <i>for Youth Sport Coaches</i>	<p>The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they coach:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="523 1055 1492 2047"> <tr> <td data-bbox="523 1055 1005 1462"> <p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners’ interests and needs, feedback strategies to learners • items of risks of sedentary behavior • range of benefits of daily physical activity • proper test items / manuals for measurement of different motor and sport skills </td> <td data-bbox="1005 1055 1492 1462"> <p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to apply knowledge, to monitor/evaluate motor skills and sport skills development, to prepare feedback cards/tools • to develop individual and group exercises that are fun and engaging • use of feedback tools and strategies (e.g., feedback cards) </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="523 1462 1005 2047"> <p>Attitudes: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to serve as a role model for children and adolescents regarding enthusiasm for daily practice of physical activity • to find creative ways of improving the development status of each child / adolescent </td> <td data-bbox="1005 1462 1492 2047"> <p>Values: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reflect and respect the individual PA status of children and adolescents • build team partnerships in the group between the best (helpers) and the worst (needers) • promote fair play within the group and the social context (e.g., parents) </td> </tr> </table>		<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners’ interests and needs, feedback strategies to learners • items of risks of sedentary behavior • range of benefits of daily physical activity • proper test items / manuals for measurement of different motor and sport skills 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to apply knowledge, to monitor/evaluate motor skills and sport skills development, to prepare feedback cards/tools • to develop individual and group exercises that are fun and engaging • use of feedback tools and strategies (e.g., feedback cards) 	<p>Attitudes: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to serve as a role model for children and adolescents regarding enthusiasm for daily practice of physical activity • to find creative ways of improving the development status of each child / adolescent 	<p>Values: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reflect and respect the individual PA status of children and adolescents • build team partnerships in the group between the best (helpers) and the worst (needers) • promote fair play within the group and the social context (e.g., parents)
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to empower children and adolescents for self-directed engagement in PA 	
Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i>	The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to support the children they coach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):	
	Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> how much PA is necessary a day to develop a healthy lifestyle what are FMS and FSS why aerobic endurance/walking, biking/running is beneficial 	Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> how can I monitor my status of motor and sport skills how can I help and assist for mentoring motor and sport skills development in the team / group assessment of benchmarks of development, at risks level, healthy zones
	Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> practice a variety of different motor / sport skills on moderate to vigorous PA level be motivated to exercise each day for 60 min. to help others and to become a partner of less skilled teammates 	Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> communication & cooperation in the group/team respect everyone regardless of his/her performance level be a fair player
Connection to other Core Module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Module 4: Fundamental Movement Skills and Play 	

Course Structure

Course Title	Needs and Benefits of Daily Physical Activities		
Course Number	1.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The course provides the collection of physical, psychosocial and mental needs to avoid risks of individual development and what are the benefits of age-related daily physical activities for children and adolescents.</p> <p>In summary, it lines out with support of self-directed learning what a holistic approach of development needs as essential criteria and facts for a well-rounded quality of education.</p>		
Course Structure	L	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: The Needs and Benefits of Daily PA
	S	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: The holistic concept of personal development through daily PA
	SDL	6 h	Teaching Unit 3: Independent Project
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The needs and benefits of daily PA from physical, psychosocial and mental perspective WHO. EU and national guidelines Physical literacy and its domains – Think, Feel and Do 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concept of holistic development (Physical literacy) Specifics of motor, cognitive, and socio-emotional development of 5 – 12 year old children The importance of an holistic approach from the aspect of physical activity 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Independent Project: For a target age group, identify the benefits of PA for children, the types of PA that suit children and the approach to be taken in the development of motor, cognitive, and socio-emotional development of children. 	

Course Title	Monitoring and Assessment of Fundamental Movement Skills and Sport Skills		
Course Number	1.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The course refers to different age-related approaches of monitoring Fundamental Movement Skills (FMS) and Sport Skills (SK) as well as Physical Literacy (PL) for children and adolescents. The approaches, batteries and items of monitoring should fit into popular field tests which can be applied with simple tools in the gym and on the pitch. Age-related cut off points for regular development and developments at unhealthy risk level should be known as well as for accelerated, gifted children and adolescents.</p> <p>Each learner should develop the ability to be a competent and reliable conductor of each test.</p>		
Course Structure	L	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Age-related tools of monitoring FMS and SK and cognitive and affective domains of PL with field-based batteries and items of measurement
	S	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Age-related criteria and cut off points of assessments of healthy development and at risk level
	SDL	4 h	Teaching Unit 3: How to Apply Test Batteries and Items for Monitoring and Measurement of Children and Adolescents
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> field tests of FMS and SK development Tests for cognitive and affective domains of PL monitoring criteria and applications for measurement 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer application and analysis of results (develop ability to conducted each test reliably) Collection of assessment criteria and cut off points to evaluate children Adolescents at risk and in healthy developmental zones for FMS and SK / cognitive and affective domains of PL 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application with children and analysis of results age-related tool kits for measurement in the gym and on the pitch 	

Course Title	Applying toolkits and test items for measurement and assessment		
Course Number	1.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	After summary of the outcome of teaching units/ seminars in courses No. 1.1 and 1.2, preparation starts in the lecture to go into the field of measurement and assessment (gym, pitch) in order to apply knowledge and skills in workshop followed by two parts (data collection, data analysis and assessment). Self-directed learning will finally support and extend personal experiences of the workshop.		
Course Structure	L	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Transfer of Knowledge into Practice
	W / PE	6 h	Teaching Unit 2: Data Collection and Data Analysis
	SDL	4 h	Teaching Unit 3: Documentation of individual measurement results
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What we learned and how to apply our knowledge in the gym/on the pitch for measurement and assessments • Planning for visit to schools / clubs • Organization of testing equipment • Timetable for explanation to children, data collection, analysis of results and presentation back to children 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applying the tests with Children from data collection to preparation of reports of results) • Prepare a stationary of measurement, prepare each station of the test and conduct measurement of the item of the test battery • analysis and evaluation of the collected data compared to given age-related cut off points/healthy zones of measurement results 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of results and implications for each child • Documentation of individual measurement result • student-centered protocols • formats for feedback reports 	